

BRAND BUILDING OF TOUR OF ZHONGYUAN ROAD OPEN CYCLING CHAMPIONSHIP

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Abstract

The Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling, which originated in 2015, is a key construction project of Henan Province's Healthy Central Plains 2030 Plan, Henan Province's 14th Five Year Plan for Sports Development, and Henan Province's Action Plan for Promoting High Quality Development of the Sports Industry. It is also a highly influential individual mass sports event in China. On the basis of imitating the environmental laws and the Qinghai Lake, Tour of ZhongYuan has gradually established its unique brand image through market-oriented operation, combined with its own special development environment. How to develop faster, better, and more sustainably is an important issue currently facing. This study takes brand building as the starting point and constructs a structural equation model that affects brand building through quantitative research methods. It further analyzes the impact of brand positioning, brand value, destination image, and brand loyalty on brand building. This study was conducted using 363 questionnaire data and processed and analyzed using SPSS and AMOS software. This study has four research objectives: 1. To investigate the current status of brand positioning, brand value, perception of destination, and brand loyalty in the brand building of the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling. 2. To Analyze the impact of brand positioning, brand value, perception of destination, and brand loyalty on the brand building of the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling. 3. To Create a model for the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling to establish branding, brand positioning, brand value, perception of destination and brand loyalty. 4. To evaluate the impact of brand positioning, brand value, perception of destination, and brand loyalty on the brand building of the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling. The results indicate that: Brand positioning has a significant positive impact on perception of destination. Brand positioning has a significant positive impact on Brand Loyalty. Brand Value has a significant positive impact on perception of destination. Brand Value has a significant positive impact on Brand Loyalty. Perception of destination has a significant positive impact on Brand Building. Brand Loyalty has a significant positive impact on Brand Building. Brand positioning has a significant positive impact on Brand Building. Brand Value has a significant positive impact on Brand Building. The destination perception of the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling has a mediating effect on brand positioning and brand building. The destination perception of the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling Race plays a mediating role in the impact between brand value and brand building. The brand loyalty of the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling Race plays a mediating role between brand positioning and brand building. The brand loyalty of the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling Race plays a mediating role between brand value and brand building.

Keywords: The Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling; Brand Positioning; Perception of Destination; Brand Loyalty; Brand Value; Brand Building.

1. INTRODUCTION

Starting from the strategy of brand building, by analyzing the internal and external strategic environment of the organization, as well as the organization's own resources and capabilities, selecting and formulating appropriate brand positioning, implementing brand values well, strengthening the management and control of event destinations, and effectively playing the key role of brand loyalty, in order to establish a good brand image, enhance the advantages of event brands, and enhance the competitiveness of China's sports event brands internationally.

China, with a population of over 1.3 billion, is known as the "Kingdom of Bicycles" and the "country on the wheels of bicycles" due to its ownership of 600 million bicycles. With the improvement of living standards, people's awareness of health and environmental protection is increasing day by day. More and more people value the fitness value of cycling. China's competitive cycling and amateur cycling have developed rapidly. In the 2000 Sydney Olympics, Jiang Cuihua won a bronze medal in the women's meter time trial, breaking the record of zero Olympic medals for China. In the 2021 Tokyo Olympics, Zhong Angel and Bao Shanju won gold medals in the women's team track cycling race. In the 14th National Games of the People's Republic of China, the Henan cycling team achieved an impressive record of 4 gold, 2 silver, and 3 bronze medals in the track cycling competition. As the highlight of the Henan delegation before the opening of the National Games, the cycling team fired a beautiful "cannon". The professional level of cycling in Henan belongs to the true strength of Henan's competitive sports. While the level of competitive cycling has rapidly improved, the mass cycling sport in China has shown a vigorous development trend, with countless people becoming cycling enthusiasts and many amateur cycling races scattered throughout the country. The Henan Province Central Plains Highway Cycling Open is a well-known large-scale amateur cycling event.

The Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling, which originated in 2015, is a key construction project of Henan Province's "Healthy Central Plains 2030 Plan", Henan Province's "14th Five Year Plan for Sports Development", and Henan Province's "Action Plan for Promoting High Quality Development of the Sports Industry". It is also the amateur cycling event with the most cross classic tourist destinations and the longest cycling distance around scenic areas in Henan Province. It is also a highly influential individual mass sports event in China. On the basis of emulating the special environment of development in the environment around France and Qinghai Lake, Tour of Zhongyuan has gradually established its unique brand image through market-oriented operations. In just 7 years, it has made tremendous progress. Although there is a huge gap in competition level, commercial value, and brand development compared to mature competitions such as France and Qinghai Lake, its potential market vitality and development prospects are worth looking forward to.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Brand building refers to creating a brand image that influences and promotes an event through a series of planned strategies and actions in sports, entertainment, or other fields. The goal of event brand building is to create a unique, competitive, and powerful brand that attracts more

participants, audiences, sponsors, and media attention, thereby enhancing the impact and commercial value of the event. Brand building for sports events is a long-term and comprehensive process that requires continuous efforts and investment to promote brand growth and development. American brand marketing experts conducted research on the relevant content of brand equity in the book "Creating Strong Brands", and emphasized the importance and role of brand identification, brand positioning, and brand personality in brand creation activities through the analysis of multiple brand building cases D. A. Aaker, (1991).

Brand positioning is the core issue of marketing, which is to find a suitable "position" in the minds or segmented markets of customer groups, so that customers can associate this product or service in a suitable and ideal way, there by maximizing potential benefits Hu Yitong, (2016). Event brand positioning is a complex process influenced by various factors, including the macro environment, industry status, event organizers, and competitors. Therefore, in the process of event positioning, multiple influencing factors should be considered Zhang Xinran, (2020).The positioning of the competition should follow the principle of differentiation, because the role of the brand is to distinguish similar products, and the positioning of the competition should also follow the principle of dynamism.

The term brand value, also known as brand equity in academia, refers to the added value that a product generates due to its brand name (Park and Srinivasan, 1994). Katherine. (2001) Subjective brand inspection by customers and exceeding objectively perceived value. This study defines destination perception as the sum of individual beliefs, thoughts, impressions, and feelings towards the destination based on time accumulation and information collection. Lawson et al. (1977) the expression of all objective knowledge, impressions, biases, imaginations, and emotional thoughts about a specific location by an individual. Crompton. (1979) the sum of a person's beliefs, thoughts, and impressions of their destination. Assael. (1984)The overall perception of a location after integrating information from different sources over a period of time.Phelps. (1986) Perception or impression of a place. Gartner et al. (1987) the impression of a place by people who do not reside there. Moutinho. (1987) the individual's attitude towards the attributes of the destination is based on their emotions and knowledge. Echtner et al. (1991) Perception of individual attributes and overall impact of the destination. Dadgostar et al. (1992) the overall impression and attitude of an individual towards a particular location. Milman et al. (1995) in summary, the main factors that affect brand building include brand positioning, brand value, destination perception, and brand loyalty. In many literature, satisfaction also plays a mediating role. These literature provide a theoretical basis for the research hypothesis of this article

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

- H1: Perception of destination has direct effect on brand positioning in Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling.
- H2: Brand building has direct effect on brand positioning in Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling.

- H3: Brand loyalty has direct effect on brand positioning in Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling.
- H4: Perception of destination has direct effect on brand value in Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling.
- H5: Brand building has direct effect on brand value in Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling.
- H6: Brand loyalty has direct effect on brand value in Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling.
- H7: Brand building has direct effect on brand positioning in Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling through the perception of destination.
- H8: Brand building has direct effect on brand value in Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling through brand loyalty.
- H9: Perception of destination and brand positioning has direct effect on brand building in Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling.
- H10: Brand loyalty and brand value has direct effect on brand building in Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling through.

Figure 1: Variable structure diagram

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

According to the above literature, the brand construction of the Central Plains Road Cycling Open is influenced by many factors, including brand positioning, brand value, destination perception, and brand loyalty. Based on the hypotheses proposed by multiple scholars, the author created a survey questionnaire on brand construction for the Central Plains Highway Cycling Open. After multiple on-site distribution of questionnaires, a total of 390 were collected, and 363 valid questionnaires were collected. The author used SPSS and AMOS software to organize and analyze questionnaire data, and constructed structural equation models for brand positioning, brand value, destination perception, and brand loyalty. Through confirmatory factor analysis, a structural equation model for brand positioning, brand value, destination perception, and brand loyalty was ultimately constructed to test the credibility and effectiveness of the structural equation model.

5. STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELLING

Combined with the hypotheses of the previous research, structural equation modelling was constructed and the correlation lines between the independent variables were drawn, and substituting the data into AMOS 26 yielded the following results.

Figure 2: Operating results of structural equation model diagram (standardized)

The fitting indicators for model operation are shown in the table 4.29, and the fitting indicator situation is: $\chi^2 / Df = 1.255$, less than 5. $GFI = 0.955$, $AGFI = 0.938$, $IFI = 0.984$, $TLI = 0.981$, $CFI = 0.984$, greater than 0.8, $RMSEA = 0.027$, less than 0.08. The fitting standards of the control table and the fitting indicators of the structural equation model meet the requirements, making it suitable for model analysis. This study used AMOS26.0 software for structural equation

model path analysis, in order to obtain the values of the structural equation model path coefficient and C R. The value and path coefficient reflect the relationship and degree of influence between variables, with a critical ratio of C R. (Critical Ratio) can determine whether the regression coefficient is significant or not, and it is generally believed that C R. A value greater than or equal to 1.96 indicates a significant difference at the 0.05 level (Hou Jietai, Wen Zhonglin, 2005). The standardized regression coefficients and variance parameter estimates of the model in this study are shown in the table 1.

Table 1: Path coefficients between variables

Regression path			β	b	S.E.	C.R.	P
perception of destination	←	Brand positioning	0.304	0.337	0.070	4.802	***
Brand Loyalty	←	Brand positioning	0.206	0.232	0.072	3.212	0.001
perception of destination	←	Brand Value	0.316	0.415	0.099	4.190	***
Brand Loyalty	←	Brand Value	0.435	0.579	0.113	5.128	***
Brand Building	←	perception of destination	0.212	0.193	0.064	3.019	0.003
Brand Building	←	Brand Loyalty	0.258	0.231	0.070	3.295	***
Brand Building	←	Brand positioning	0.161	0.163	0.065	2.499	0.012
Brand Building	←	Brand Value	0.214	0.255	0.103	2.488	0.013

Remarks: * * *, P <0.001; B Non standardized coefficient; β : Standardization factor coefficient

6. MEDIATED EFFECTS TEST

The Bootstrap method can directly test the existence of mediating effects. The hypothesis for direct testing is $H_0: ab=0$. If the confidence interval obtained from the test results contains 0, it indicates that there is no mediating effect. Based on the results of path analysis, the hypothesis test is valid. In order to explore whether there is a mediating effect in these significant paths, we ran the Bootstrap method on AMOS 26.0, selected 5000 replicates, confidence interval standard of 95%, and bias correction method for testing...

Table 2: Mediation Effect

Regression path	Effect type	Effect	SE	95% Lower	95% Upper	P
Brand positioning→perception of destination→Brand Building	Indirect effects	0.064	0.028	0.018	0.127	0.007
	Direct effects	0.161	0.071	0.025	0.302	0.025
	Total effect	0.226	0.066	0.094	0.352	0.001
Brand positioning→Brand Loyalty→Brand Building	Indirect effects	0.053	0.025	0.015	0.118	0.002
	Direct effects	0.161	0.071	0.025	0.302	0.025
	Total effect	0.215	0.072	0.074	0.356	0.004
Brand Value→perception of destination→Brand Building	Indirect effects	0.067	0.028	0.020	0.130	0.006
	Direct effects	0.214	0.087	0.053	0.388	0.011
	Total effect	0.281	0.083	0.121	0.446	0.001
Brand Value→Brand Loyalty→Brand Building	Indirect effects	0.112	0.041	0.042	0.203	0.002
	Direct effects	0.214	0.087	0.053	0.388	0.011
	Total effect	0.326	0.072	0.186	0.467	0.001

The confidence interval for bias correction in the bootstrap of Brand positioning → perception of destination → Brand Building is [0.018, 0.127], excluding 0, indicating that the mediating effect is valid. The confidence interval for bias correction in the bootstrap of Brand positioning → Brand Loyalty → Brand Building is [0.015, 0.118], excluding 0, indicating that the mediating effect is valid. The confidence interval for bias correction in the bootstrap of Brand Value → perception of destination → Brand Building is [0.020, 0.130], excluding 0, indicating that the mediating effect is valid. The confidence interval for bias correction in the bootstrap of Brand Value → Brand Loyalty → Brand Building is [0.042, 0.203], excluding 0, indicating that the mediating effect is valid.

7. CONCLUSION

This article takes the Brand building of the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling as the research object, and studies the impact of brand positioning, brand value, destination image, and brand loyalty on brand construction. To address the aforementioned issues, this study employed both qualitative and quantitative research methods, with 390 stakeholders as the research sample. A total of 363 valid questionnaires were surveyed and collected, and descriptive statistics, exploratory analysis, reliability analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, and correlation analysis were conducted. SPSS and AMOS software were used to establish a structural equation model for the collected data, Identify the important factors that affect the brand building of cycling events. Identify the important factors that affect brand building. Finally, the following conclusion is drawn:

Brand positioning has a significant positive impact on perception of destination. Brand positioning has a significant positive impact on Brand Loyalty. Brand Value has a significant positive impact on perception of destination. Brand Value has a significant positive impact on Brand Loyalty. Perception of destination has a significant positive impact on Brand Building. Brand Loyalty has a significant positive impact on Brand Building. Brand positioning has a significant positive impact on Brand Building. Brand Value has a significant positive impact on Brand Building. The destination perception of the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling has a mediating effect on brand positioning and brand building. The destination perception of tthe Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling Race plays a mediating role in the impact between brand value and brand building. The brand loyalty of tthe Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling Race plays a mediating role between brand positioning and brand building. The brand loyalty of the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling Race plays a mediating role between brand value and brand building.

8. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Deeply explore the relationship mechanism between brand positioning and destination perception, and further clarify the impact path and mechanism between the two. Research the specific application of brand building strategies in sports event brand building, and explore the impact of different brand building strategies on brand image and value. Examine the characteristics and laws of brand building for different types of sports events, compare the

practical experience of brand building for different types of sports events, and provide reference for brand building for different types of sports events. Analyze consumer perceptions and attitudes towards sports event brands, explore the impact of consumer participation on sports event brand construction, and provide a basis for enhancing the image and value of sports event brands. This study is the author's first study on the factors that affect the brand construction of the Tour of ZhongYuan Road Open Cycling. After the preliminary research results are formed, a more comprehensive and in-depth investigation will be conducted. In order to select a more comprehensive survey sample, a survey will be conducted on the construction of road bicycle brands in various regions of China in the later stage, enriching the composition of the sample and helping to understand the basic situation of the overall construction of bicycle sports brands.

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